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Model assisted reliability assessment for adhesive bonding quality evaluation with advanced ultrasonic NDT

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Abstract

This work proposes a novel cost-effective technique to evaluate the reliability of advanced ultrasonic non-destructive testing technique in bonding quality evaluation. Detectability of debonding defects and weak bonds in aluminum-epoxy single lap joints was estimated by model assisted probability of detection curves. For those adhesive joints containing three different bonding qualities –debonding at interface, weak bond with release agent contamination, and weak bond due to faulty curing– numerical models were built. Ultrasonic wave propagation is simulated by using semi-analytical finite element method via CIVA and validated with experimental investigations. In order to create a variation study, uncertain parameters and their distribution is determined based on experiments and expertise. Ultrasonic signal responses in time and frequency domain are analyzed as opposed to defect characteristic values. According to reliability analysis, it is shown that the detection probability of debonding is mostly based on the gate selection and ultrasonic echo amplitude, while weak bond detection requires a more delicate assessment. Frequency based calculations can improve the detection reliability of weak bond due to release agent contamination. Weak bonds caused by faulty curing are more sensitive to be detected via the attenuation of signal response.

Keywords: Model assisted probability of detection (PoD), adhesive bonds, ultrasonics, acoustic microscopy

1. Introduction

Adhesive bonding is an advantageous joining technology with the characteristics as homogenous load distribution, high strength to weight ratio, ability to join dissimilar materials and complex structures.

The durability of adhesively bonded structures might be affected during or after manufacturing by moisture, contamination or poor curing [1]. These variations might cause different type of defects [2], and even weak bonds – unreliable bonding quality hardly detectable by classical non-destructive testing (NDT) methods [3,4]. The lack of knowledge in NDT reliability is the key factor limiting adhesive bonding applications in regulated industries such as aerospace [5]. NDT reliability is usually quantified with Probability of Detection (PoD) curves [6], which relates the probability of detecting a defect with its characteristic value – usually considered to be the defect size [7,8]. While each nondestructive test is valid for the specific specimen, the detectability of defects is influenced by multiple uncontrollable factors like environmental conditions (temperature, radiation, moisture), inspection properties (experimental set-up and condition, control related uncertainties, digital and analog noise), human factors (personnel qualifications, experience, overwork) and variance occurring in specimens (material and dimensional properties) [9,10].

In practice, the reliability determination of NDT technique is a costly and time-consuming procedure that requires a large number of specimens and personnel. While experimental PoD curves are challenging to achieve, the need and acceptance of PoD curves for safety regulations are increasing. Therefore, the industries like aerospace are turning their face to simulation based reliability analysis, model assisted probability of detection (MAPOD) [11–13]. Use of simulation for PoD curve generation not only reduces the time and budget but also allows systematic work to be carried out. By using MAPOD large amount of data can be analyzed, even with configurations that are not possible to achieve experimentally [13,14].

MAPOD has been a research interest of many studies with applications on eddy current testing (for fatigue cracks in engine components [15], wing lap joints [15], in titanium plates [16]), induction thermography (for crack detection [17]) and ultrasonic NDT (defects in engine disk alloys [15], in railway axles [18]). A detailed review has been reported by Meyer et.al in 2014 [19]. Recently, Bato et.al compared experimental PoD with MAPOD estimations for eddy current testing of surface fatigue cracks [7]. Additionally, Baskaran et.al integrated two features as response signals with MAPOD for

the evaluation of flaw detectability with eddy current testing [20]. Jarvis et. al utilized MAPOD to estimate response operating characteristic curves on magnetic field measurements [21]. Rentala et.al highlighted the procedure and challenges to obtain MAPOD curves with a case study on flat bottom hole detection by ultrasonic NDT [22]. Also, Smagulova et al evaluated the reliability to detect debonding in dissimilar joints with ultrasonic testing by using MAPOD [23].

PoD curves can be obtained by two methods: hit-miss technique (binary method, defect is detected or not) and signal response analysis (where characteristic defect value (a) is compared with NDT response (\hat{a})). Most MAPOD analysis are based on signal response analysis (a vs. \hat{a}) because numerical simulations allow recording signal response easily [19]. For ultrasonic testing, absolute maximum amplitudes (A_{max}) and time of flight difference (TOFD) methods are the most common signal responses in PoD curve calculations [24,25]. However, post-processing for the signal response selection plays an important role in the nondestructive evaluation of adhesive bonding quality since the probability of defect detection is low due to the structural noise caused by interface echoes for ultrasonic wave propagation [26] and thermal diffusion [27]. In general, ultrasonic defect characterization uncertainty might be reduced by using multiple features based on amplitude, phase, and frequency information [28]. In our previous work, it was demonstrated that the post-processing of ultrasonic interface echoes in frequency domain might increase the detectability of weak bonds that are weakened via release agent contamination [29].

This work aims to evaluate the reliability of debonding and weak bond detection with high frequency ultrasonic NDT by using MAPOD curves. In order to achieve this goal, three cases in aluminum-epoxy single lap joint were investigated with different bonding qualities: debonding, weak bond due to release agent contamination, and weak bond due to faulty curing. Nondestructive evaluation of the adhesive joints was performed by scanning acoustic microscopy in pulse-echo mode. Numerical models were built and ultrasonic wave propagation was simulated with semi-analytical finite element software CIVA [12]. After model validation, the metamodels are built by variances in uncertain parameters which are determined by design of experiments and expertise. For each bonding quality

case, different defect properties were selected as characteristic values: defect length in debonding, inclusion thickness in weak bond due to release agent, acoustic wave velocity of epoxy in weak bond due to faulty curing. Five different features are evaluated as signal response: peak to peak amplitude, time delay, frequency domain absolute maximum amplitude, frequency shift, attenuation. PoD curves are reported for all bonding quality cases with each feature in signal response.

2. Materials/Samples

Aluminum-epoxy single-lap adhesive joints with various bonding qualities have been manufactured in Cotesa GmbH, Germany. Two identical 1.6 mm thick aluminum 2024 sheets have been bonded together with 3M Scotch-Weld AF163 k-red structural adhesive film epoxy. For all samples, surface preparation is done by polishing with sandpaper and acetone cleaning. Bonding quality deviated with several different techniques. For reference, one sample has been produced with nominal settings, without any inclusion, and named as “perfect bond - PB” (Figure 1-a, right side II). The delamination at the bonding interface is demonstrated by adding square double-fold Wrigtлон 4600 release film (12.7 mm edge length, 0.063 mm thick) and named “debonding-DB” (Figure 1-a, left side I).

In addition, weak bonds scenario due to contamination of adhesive-adherend interface is replicated by adding Marbocote release agent prior to bonding and named as “weak bond due to release agent – WB-RA”. Different amounts of release agent were applied: 1ml/5500 mm² marked as thick inclusion, 0.2 ml/5500 mm² marked as thin inclusion. Lastly, in order to represent possible heating protocol deviations, the curing cycle for the bonding epoxy has been altered, and named “weak bond due to faulty curing – WB-FC”. While the standard cure temperature for AF163-K epoxy is 125°C, two poor curing specimens have been manufactured at 90°C and 75°C.

Figure 1 Sample pictures prior to bonding (a) Artificial debonding and perfect bond sample (b) weak bond release agent sample, epoxy covered with release agent.

3. Methodology

In order to evaluate the reliability of advanced ultrasonic nondestructive testing methods with model based probability of detection curves, a detailed study with multiple steps has been conducted (Figure 2). Firstly, the experimental analysis on samples has been performed and the ultrasonic echoes from the bonding region have been recorded. Then the numerical models were built to find the best match of the variable parameters to the experimental results. By careful consideration, separate experiments, and NDT experts' suggestions, uncertain parameters and their distribution were determined. Characteristic values for the metamodels were defined for each bonding quality. Numerical experiments were performed to obtain the characteristic value versus signal response curves. Statistical analysis was performed on the data to obtain the probability of detection curves. The threshold value was selected based on the separate calculations of background noise, which is considered to be adhesive bond without any defect (perfect bond-PB).

Figure 2 Methodological steps to obtain model based probability of detection curves.

3.1. Ultrasonic Non-destructive testing

Adhesively bonded aluminum-epoxy-aluminum single-lap joints with different bonding qualities have been investigated with scanning acoustic microscopy (KSI GmbH) at Ultrasound Research Institute, Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania. The schematic of the inspection system is shown in Figure 3-a. Samples were investigated in a temperature controlled room (25°C) with immersion pulse-echo technique. Focused ultrasonic transducer which has 50 MHz central frequency, 3 mm aperture, and

10 mm focal distance in water (PT-50-3-10) is selected. In order to keep the transducer focus at the sample interface, the distance between the transducer and the sample is kept at 2.94 mm.

Figure 3 Sketch of scanning acoustic microscopy experimental set-up (a) and the numerical model for the ultrasonic wave propagation simulation with CIVA (b).

3.2. Numerical model and its validation

Numerical models of aluminum-epoxy single lap joints have been built and ultrasonic wave propagation was simulated with semi-analytical finite element method via CIVA software (CEA, Fr) (Figure 3-b). CIVA allows to define material parameters and inspection settings prior to simulation. Also, the excitation signal can be uploaded for ultrasonic wave propagation calculation. In this work excitation signal is recorded by scanning a standard reference thick aluminum block with acoustic microscopy with the same transducer. In order to reduce the computation time that is increased by multi-layer structure and high frequency, two dimensional calculations were performed. Each case of bonding quality has been studied carefully and the numerical models are validated by the experimental results.

Figure 4 Schematics for aluminum-epoxy single-lap joints with different bonding quality: a) perfect bond-PB, b) debonding-DB, c) weak bond due to release agent (oil) inclusion – WB-RA, d) weak bond due to faulty curing – WB-FC.

Aluminum-epoxy-aluminum three-layer model has been built as the base for the ultrasonic wave propagation medium. The adhesive-adherend interfaces are modeled to be continuously in contact. For debonding defect, a rectangular defect has been placed at the top interface. An example of experimental A-scan response for perfect bond and debonding specimens are shown together with numerical results in Figure 5. It can be noticed that the ultrasonic echo signal shape and frequency of the experimental signal have been preserved in numerical calculations. While there is a small delay in numerical results, this might be related to the variations of the sample.

Figure 5 A-scan comparison for numerical model validations. (a) Perfect bond-PB, (b) Debonding-DB.

Numerical results show similar parameters as experimental results: debonding presence increases the top reflection amplitude, whereas bottom reflection is only observed in perfect bond (Figure 6). Also, it is observed that the presence of debonding at the top interface blocks the ultrasonic wave and no echo at the bottom interface, from 4.57 to 4.62 μs in time domain is visible.

Figure 6 Experimental (I) and numerical (II) results for perfect bond (blue dashed line -PB) and debonding (red continuous line- DB) samples. Recorded and simulated ultrasonic A-scan results (a) and F-scan (frequency domain) with gate at top interface(b) is shown.

An extra oil layer has been added in between aluminum and epoxy interface to represent weak bond due to release agent inclusion (WB-RA). As seen in Figure 7, the addition of an oil layer as thin as 0.05 mm at the interface, affects the ultrasonic echo received at the transducer. Numerical results agree with the experimental ones that the bottom interface reflection amplitude decreases and the flight time of bottom reflection reception differ from the perfect bond. On the other hand, while numerical results show that there is a slight increase in amplitude in top interface reflection, this has not been observed in the experimental results. Therefore, time gate is considered to be at the bottom interface reflection flight time -from 4.57 to 4.62 μs - for WB-RA.

Figure 7 Experimental (I) and numerical (II) results for perfect bond (blue dashed line -PB), weak bond due to release agent thin inclusion (yellow continuous line- RA Thin), and weak bond due to release agent thick contamination (dotted green line- RA thick) samples. Recorded and simulated ultrasonic A-scan results (a) and F-scan (frequency domain) with gate at top interface(b) is shown.

Additionally, weak bond due to faulty curing is represented by the change in epoxy acoustic wave velocity – which is expected to be affected due to cure temperature dependence of material elasticity.

As seen in Figure 8, in both experimental and numerical cases, top interface reflection has not changed due to the faulty curing. However, the bottom interface reflection amplitude is reduced slightly and the flight time of reception has been affected significantly. Hence, the second interface reflection observed –bottom reflection- has been considered to be of interest for this case.

Figure 8 Experimental (I) and numerical (II) results for perfect bond (blue dashed line -PB), weak bond due to faulty curing at 90°C (purple continuous line- FC-90°C and at 75°C (orange dotted line - FC-75°C). Recorded and simulated ultrasonic A-scan results (a) and F-scan (frequency domain) with gate at top interface(b) is shown.

3.3. Determination of uncertain parameters & their statistical distribution

The uncertain parameters and their statistical distributions are one of the key factors to obtain reliable MAPOD curves. The uncertain parameters are the parameters that might be variant due to specimen based, experimental, environmental, or human factors. In order to determine uncertain parameters, design of experiments based on Morris design has been built with a large number of variables to determine the influential parameters. As listed in Table 1, eight influential parameters are marked as uncertain parameters to be used in the variation study. The statistical distribution for each uncertain parameter has been determined by using experimental investigations and expertise.

Table 1 Uncertain parameter limits and distribution characteristics.

Name	Definition	Mean Value	Standard deviation	Min Value	Max Value	Unit [SI]
Epoxy thickness	Epoxy thickness, thickness of the adhesive.	0.16	0.012	0.12	0.24	mm
Epoxy acoustic velocity	Longitudinal acoustic wave velocity of epoxy	2990	300	1186	4706	m/s
Aluminum thickness	Aluminum thickness (top adherend)	1.6	0.007	1.59	1.66	mm
Aluminum acoustic velocity	Longitudinal acoustic wave velocity of aluminum (top)	6300	50	6200	6600	m/s
Water path	The distance between transducer and specimen	2.94	0.004	2.92	2.96	mm
Water acoustic velocity	Longitudinal acoustic wave velocity of water	1480	10	1447	1506	m/s
Incidence angle	The tilt of the transducer	0	1	-3	3	degree (angle)
Defect position (in depth)	The defect position through the thickness from surface	1.6	0.012	1.6	1.72	mm

While thickness and acoustic velocity variances observed in adhesive and adherend are classified as specimen family uncertainties; the water path, water acoustic velocity, and incidence angle are considered to be operational uncertainties due to nondestructive inspection setup and human factor. On the other hand, defect position is considered to be defect related uncertainty.

Adhesive (epoxy) and top adherend (aluminum) thicknesses and acoustic wave velocity are taken into account as specimen related uncertain parameters. Epoxy and aluminum densities are also considered to be evaluated in the first design of experiments, however, they are not labeled as influential. Although the theoretical thickness of epoxy is given as 0.24 mm in the material datasheet, due to the applied pressure during the bonding manufacturing the epoxy thickness is suspected to decrease. For each sample, after bonding, the thickness of the bonded region has been measured several times with caliper. The mean value for epoxy thickness is determined as 0.16 mm whereas the standard deviation is 0.012 mm (Table 1). Theoretical epoxy acoustic velocity is calculated based on elastic properties given in the epoxy material data sheet as 1186 m/s. Time of flight (ToF) differences for epoxy layer (from top and bottom of epoxy) are obtained with pulse-echo scanning acoustic microscopy investigations. The acoustic wave velocity (v) is estimated based on the measured thickness (th) and calculated time of flight difference (ToF) by using equation (1). While minimal value is determined as

the theoretical estimation 1186 m/s, the mean value is determined as 2990 m/s along with 300 m/s standard deviation (Table 1).

$$ToF = 2 * \frac{th}{v} \quad (1)$$

Aluminum thickness and acoustic wave velocity statistical distribution are determined by similar methodology. Top adherend thickness is measured by calipers and the acoustic wave velocity distribution is determined via scanning acoustic microscopy ultrasonic investigation. The mean value for aluminum thickness is assessed as 1.6 mm, while the deviation is 0.007 mm (Table 1). Acoustic velocity of aluminum has been estimated to change from 6200 to 6600 m/s within the sample with a standard thickness of 1.6 mm (Table 1).

Considering the surface reflection time of flights that have been recorded during experiments, the statistical distribution for water path has been determined as a mean value at 2.94 mm with 0.004 mm standard deviation (Table 1). On the other hand, the variance observed for water acoustic velocity is considered to be due to temperature changes in the experimental set-up or due to impurity content within the water (Table 1). Incidence angle, where the perpendicularity of the transducer is considered to be deviant, is set from 0 ± 3 degrees; and it can be caused by the transducer alignment or sample placement (Table 1).

The defect position for the debonding case is considered to be changing. While the interface is more susceptible to debonding defects, multiple inclusions such as release films might get stuck within the adhesive during manufacturing. Therefore, the position of the defect is considered to be mostly at the adhesive-adherend interface, and distribution is affected by the thickness of the epoxy (Table 1). For the debonding case, the thickness of adherend (aluminum at top) has been considered to be constant at 1.6 mm in order to be able to simulate the defect always within adhesive with variance at the defect position.

3.4. Characteristic value determination & limits

The physical characteristics of the weakening indifferent bonding quality cases help to determine the characteristic value for reliability analysis. In the debonding numerical model, where debonding is

represented with zero-thickness rectangular defect, the defect size is considered as characteristic value. The thickness of oil addition has been selected as the characteristic value for weak bond due to release agent models (WB-RA). The epoxy acoustic velocity –which is significantly affected by poor curing caused by elasticity changes, is selected as the characteristic value for weak bond due to faulty curing (WB-FC). The limits for characteristic values are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Characteristic values for each bonding quality and their limits; where DB is debonding, WB-RA is weak bond due to release agent, WB-FC is weak bond due to faulty curing.

Bonding Quality	Characteristic Value	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Unit [SI]
DB	Defect size	0.01	5	mm
WB – RA	Oil inclusion thickness	0.005	0.1	mm
WB – FC	Epoxy acoustic velocity	1000	5000	m/s

With numerical beam computation by CIVA software, the characteristic of the transducer has been identified. The focal spot of the transducer (PT50-3-10) is determined as 0.2 mm, therefore the minimum and maximum limits for debonding defect characteristic are set to 0.01 mm - 5 mm, respectively.

The characteristic value for the weak bond due to release agent contamination is the thickness of the oil layer. Based on the correlation of the numerical validation with experimental results, the limits are set as 0.005 mm and 0.1 mm.

For the weak bond caused by faulty curing, the longitudinal acoustic velocity of epoxy is considered as the characteristic value. By changing the epoxy cure cycle, it is assumed that the elastic properties of epoxy are affected. The epoxy acoustic wave velocity is estimated based on the time of flight differences from top to bottom reflection observed in scanning acoustic microscopy investigations. According to experimental results, mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) values for time of flight differences in samples are calculated for perfect bond ($\mu=107$, $\sigma=13$ nanosecond), faulty curing at 90°C ($\mu=112$, $\sigma=7$ nanosecond), and faulty curing at 75°C ($\mu=136$, $\sigma=6$ nanosecond). Theoretically, the relationship between epoxy acoustic velocity, epoxy thickness, and resulting time of flight differences from top to bottom epoxy reflection can be defined by equation (1). Figure 9 shows the epoxy thickness on X axis, epoxy acoustic velocity on Y axis and time of flight difference as the color

scale. The limits on the color axis have been determined according to $\mu \pm 3\sigma$ values calculated in the experimental data analysis. The assumption of elastic property change is supported by experimental results: when there is a reduction in curing temperature, measured acoustic wave velocity is decreased (Figure 9). While mean epoxy longitudinal acoustic velocity is 2990 m/s for perfectly cured adhesive; poor curing at 90°C resulted in 2857 m/s acoustic velocity. Faulty curing at 75°C is estimated to have 2352 m/s acoustic velocity in epoxy – that is the lowest value among all investigated samples.

Figure 9 Epoxy acoustic velocity limitations for different bonding qualities (b: perfect bond, c: faulty curing at 90°C, d: faulty curing at 75°C) based on experimental calculations.

3.5. Numerical simulations and post-processing

Validated numerical models for each bonding quality have been used as reference models for the metamodel study. Metamodels, also known as response surfaces, are mathematical approximations that are used to reduce the computation time of high degrees of freedom numerical simulations [30]. The metamodels are built by implementing minimum and maximum values for each uncertain parameter as well as characteristic values. Each metamodel has more than 1000 calculation points and the Kriging method – Gaussian process regression- [30,31] has been used for interpolation.

Mostly, the metamodels are built with extracted parameters such as amplitude or flight time responses of numerical investigation. This work aims to evaluate the reliability of different features for the detection of debonding and weak bonds. Hence, for each of three bonding quality cases, metamodels have been built on five different features – which will be used as the signal response (\hat{a}) in PoD curve data plots:

- peak to peak amplitude at the specified gate (Peak to Peak Amplitude)
- time delay of absolute maximum amplitude (Time Delay)
- maximum amplitude in frequency domain (Frequency Amax)
- frequency shift of absolute maximum amplitude (Frequency Shift)
- attenuation at the adhesive layer (Attenuation)

Response values for each feature are reported in Table 3 for the numerical example A-scan and F-scan in Figure 6 Figure 7 Figure 8(II).

Table 3 Feature response values for the example A-scan F-scans shown in numerical results – Figure 5-6-7-(II), for each bonding quality: PB stands for perfect bond, top for top reflection, bottom for bottom reflection, DB is debonding, WB-RA is weak bond due to release agent, WB-FC is weak bond due to faulty curing.

Bonding Quality Features	PB	PB	DB defect size: 5mm	WB – RA inclusion: 0.05 mm	WB – FC V_{EP} : 2352 m/s
	top interface reflection	bottom interface reflection	top interface reflection	bottom interface reflection	bottom interface reflection
Peak to peak amplitude, %	138.3506	37.3949	181.7098	34.3194	36.5022
Time delay, μ s	0	0	0.001	0.059	0.030
Frequency Amax, %	10.6116	2.8994	14.3958	3.4427	2.8608
Frequency shift, MHz	0	0	4.5	14	4.5
Attenuation, %	71.730	71.730	99.645	82.644	75.651

Since bonding quality information mostly lies in the interface reflection echoes, the interested time of flight is selected at the first top and first bottom interface reflections. In debonding case, the first interface reflection – which mostly represents the defect reflection is evaluated as the first option (DB-OPTION1). In order to decrease the false-positive rates in the DB case, a special gate selection algorithm is proposed and applied (DB-OPTION2). Normally, the gate starts before the first interface reflection. If the absolute maximum amplitude of the signal response is less than 100 percent and the second reflection observed, then the gate is placed at the second interface reflection. For weak bond due to release agent WB-RA and weak bond due to faulty curing WB-FC, second reflection (the wave packet observed after the top interface reflection) is of interest.

3.6. Statistical Processing: Signal response (a vs. \hat{a}) analysis

In order to obtain PoD curves, the data plots have been created via CIVA software. Based on each metamodel – representing five features for three bonding quality cases, statistical settings have been set to satisfy both normality and variance rules based on Beren’s hypothesis validity [13]. In this procedure, best fit is selected by mapping the signal response data (a vs. \hat{a}) in logarithmic, normal and boxcox settings. Some of the data has been set as “noise” and “saturation” in order to minimize the fitting errors and satisfy Beren’s validity on linearity, homoscedasticity, normality, and variance.

3.7. PoD curves – threshold selection

In addition to noise and saturation, the selection of threshold plays a significant role in PoD curve results. In this study, threshold selection is done by performing a variation study where no defect is present (perfect bond-PB) and uncertain parameters are applied. The results have been extracted for each feature and plotted against defect present cases as histogram densities. The amount of data in the PB data set which is above the threshold is calculated as probability of false alarms. According to MH-1823, no probability of detection is considered to be sufficient if the probability of false alarm is not calculated [8]. While in most standard NDT PoD studies, noise is considered to be the noise due to environmental or instrumental issues, in the case of adhesive joint inspections the highest “noise” is due to the bonding interface reflections. In each case, the threshold value is selected by taking most of the signal response into account and minimizing the probability of false alarms (PFA). In Figure 10, numerically calculated perfect bond, debonding and weak bond signal responses are represented as distributions along with threshold selection and calculated PFA percentages.

4. Results

Reliability analysis based on the numerical models for aluminum-epoxy adhesive bonding has been performed by following steps described in Figure 2. Model based probability of detection curves are reported for three different bonding qualities and five different features in Figure 11. Results are categorized by bonding quality cases:

- Case 1: Debonding (DB).

- Option 1 – where the ultrasonic time gate is selected on top interface reflection.
- Option 2 – where “smart” gate selection algorithm is applied.
- Case 2: Weak bond due to release agent (WB-RA).
- Case 3: Weak bond due to faulty curing (WB-FC).

Figure 10 Perfect bond data distribution along with debonding and weak bond for each signal response, in order to determine threshold value and calculate probability of false alarms (PFA) for debonding DB option 1 (a), debonding DB option 2 (b), weak bond due to release agent WB-RA (c), weak bond due to faulty curing WB-FC (d); for five different signal response features I-peak to peak amplitude, II- time delay, III- frequency Amax, IV-frequency shift, V-Attenuation

Figure 11 Estimated MAPOD curves for four different bonding quality cases (a) debonding DB – option 1 gate selection, (b) debonding DB – option 2 gate selection, (c) weak bond due to release agent WB – RA, (d) weak bond due to faulty curing WB – FC; considering five signal response features on the rows I- peak to peak amplitude, II- time delay, III- frequency Amax, IV- frequency shift, V- attenuation.

4.1. Case 1: Debonding (DB)

Reliability of detecting debonding defects placed at the interface of aluminum-epoxy single-lap joints is estimated based on numerical simulations. In order to create the variance in signal response, seven uncertain parameters were defined with distributions listed in Table 1, except aluminum thickness due to the counter interaction with defect depth. The defect size changing from 0.01 mm to 5 mm is used as characteristic value (a). Five response signals (\hat{a}) are estimated by post-processing during

metamodel creation: peak to peak amplitude, time delay, frequency domain maximum amplitude, frequency shift, and attenuation.

Firstly, the defect detection has been done with gate position at the maximum amplitude observed; first peak of the interface reflection – named as DB- OPTION 1. MAPOD curves are shown in Figure 11-(a) for response signals as peak-to-peak amplitude (I), time delay (II), frequency domain amplitude (III), and frequency shift (IV). The results indicate that none of the PoD curves have reached the critical stage where $a_{90/95}$ values are observed. The false calls for peak-to-peak amplitude is as high as 53 %, while time delay is almost 90 %. This behavior is associated with false-positive rates within the calculation, where the response values are high however no defect is present.

In order to improve the reliability of the inspection, we propose a “smart” gate selection algorithm: the time gate is at the first peak observed (after surface reflection) unless the maximum amplitude is less than 100 % and there is no second peak observed in short interval. This algorithm allows to search for the bottom reflection echo, while not interfering with the small amplitude reflections due to small or disoriented defect sizes. The results are marked as DB-OPTION 2 for peak-to-peak amplitude (I), time delay (II), frequency Amax (III), frequency shift (IV), and attenuation (V) (Figure 11-(b)). By comparing standard gate selection, the reliability of detecting debonding defects in bonding has increased significantly. Except for time delay feature, in all other signal responses, it is calculated that 5mm defect size can be detected with 100 percent probability. In addition, probability of false alarms is drastically lower (< 10%) than in the previous case - except for the frequency shift response signal.

4.2. Case 2: Weak bond due to release agent contamination

Interface contamination of aluminum-epoxy adhesive joints is simulated with numerical models containing a small inclusion layer of oil with seven uncertain parameters as variants (Table 1, except defect position). The oil thickness, in other words, the thickness of the inclusion, from 5 μm to 100 μm has been used as the characteristic value. Five different features are extracted as the signal response during metamodel calculation: peak to peak amplitude change, time delay, frequency domain

maximum amplitude change, frequency shift, and attenuation. The gate was selected at the second signal wave packet, the one observed after top interface reflection.

Model based probability of detection curves and transformed data plots, along with the probability of false calls can be seen in Figure 11-(c). Results show that the detection probability of a small layer of inclusion is higher in the case of peak-to-peak amplitude change (I) or attenuation (V) signal responses. On the other hand, frequency Amax change (III) and frequency shift (IV) suggest that the probability of detecting thick oil inclusion is higher than the probability of detecting thin layers of oil.

4.3. Case 3: Weak bond due to faulty curing

In order to evaluate the detection probability of weak bonds due to faulty curing, the aluminum-epoxy single lap joints are modeled by considering six uncertain parameters (Table 1, except defect position and epoxy acoustic velocity); whereas epoxy acoustic velocity is a characteristic value. Five different signal responses are considered to be of interest: peak-to-peak amplitude change, time delay, frequency domain Amax, frequency shift and attenuation. The probability of detection curves and transformed data plots are shown in Figure 11-(d) side by side.

While the probability of detecting weak bonds due to faulty curing is quite insignificant with peak-to-peak amplitude (I) and time delay (II) response signals, frequency domain based responses (III-IV) show better performance. It should be noted that the probability of false alarm for frequency shift (IV) signal response is 90 %. On the contrary, by attenuation (V) percentage the weak bond due to faulty curing can be detected with a small probability of false calls, and high performance.

5. Discussion

Model assisted PoD curves are obtained for debonding (DB), weak bond due to release agent (WB-RA), and weak bond due to faulty curing detection with scanning acoustic microscopy. For each bonding quality, five different signal responses are calculated with post-processing during metamodel simulations. MAPOD curves are represented in the results section (Figure 11).

Firstly, the debonding defect detection reliability is estimated by analyzing first interface reflections through 0.01 mm to 5 mm defect sizes (DB- OPTION 1, Figure 11-(a)). It is observed that the detection

probability for debonding with this method is low, none of the signal response data has resulted with $a_{90/95}$ indicator. The false alarm rates are also observed to be high which is caused by the high signal responses observed without defect presence. As seen in Figure 6, both experimental and numerical A-scan and F-scan response differences between debonding defect (DB) and perfect bond (PB) are quite similar for the top interface reflection. Although the bottom interface reflection is only observed in the PB case. Hence, a new time gate is defined with “smart” algorithm: the wave packet of interest is the first interface reflection unless its absolute maximum amplitude is lower than 100 percent (when calibrated at 5 mm defect with nominal values) and the bottom reflection is present. The reliability results are updated with “smart” gate selection and reported as DB-OPTION 2 in (Figure 11-(b)). Compared to DB OPTION-1, the calculated reliability of the debonding detection has increased between 10% to 30 % for debonding detection probability. The signal responses- peak-to-peak amplitude, frequency A_{max} , and attenuation have reached 100 % PoD for DB-OPTION 2 with a relatively small probability of false alarms. Whereas features like time delay and frequency shift seem to be not prioritized for defect size characteristic value. However, it should be noted that time delay and frequency shift features might significantly impact the detection probability in the case defect position is more variant.

In case 2, weak bond due to release agent contamination detection is simulated with oil layer addition to the aluminum-epoxy interface. Time domain amplitude based features, namely peak-to-peak amplitude and attenuation, show that the detection probability will decrease with the increase in contamination thickness (Figure 11-(c)). On the contrary, the frequency domain based calculations (frequency A_{max} and frequency shift) indicate that detection of a high level contamination is increased by the signal response. The frequency shift feature is the most promising signal response observed in order to detect oil based contamination in adhesive bonding. These results support the previous work based on composite-epoxy experiments [29].

In case 3, a weak bond due to faulty curing is investigated by considering epoxy acoustic velocity as a characteristic value. The best reliability performance between different signal responses is observed

by attenuation for this case (Figure 11-(d)). If attenuation signal response is excluded, frequency domain based features perform better than time domain responses; however, the frequency shift signal response shows quite a high false-positive alarm rate.

For convenience, the PoD indicator $a_{90/95}$ and probability of false alarms for each bonding quality and each signal response feature are given in Table 4, as rows and columns, respectively. In the debonding case, $a_{90/95}$ indicator is not observed with DB-OPTION1. By implementing “smart” gate the debonding defect detection as small as 0.312 mm can be achieved with 90 percent probability and 95 percent confidence interval with a peak-to-peak signal response. While attenuation $a_{90/95}$ value is the second best, frequency Amax is third and the frequency shift is the last. Time delay response signal cannot achieve $a_{90/95}$ reliability even with smart gate. The PoD indicator $a_{90/95}$ suggests that the best signal response algorithm to detect weak bond due to release agent (WB-RA) is frequency shift, where 51.38 μm thick oil contamination can be detected. However, the probability of false alarm results suggest that by 10 μm thickness trade-off the frequency amplitude might be a good choice for WB-RA detection. In case of weak bond due to faulty curing (WB-FC), $a_{90/95}$ values suggest that the best detection would be with frequency shift with 2419 m/s change. However, the false-positive call percentages show that the attenuation and frequency Amax are the best candidates to detect WB-FC with high reliability.

Table 4 Estimated POD indicator $a_{90/95}$ values and probability of false alarms for each bonding quality deviation and each feature.

Bonding Quality Features	DB – OPTION 1		DB –OPTION 2		WB-RA		WB-FC	
	$a_{90/95}$ [mm]	PFA [%]	$a_{90/95}$ [mm]	PFA [%]	$a_{90/95}$ [μm]	PFA [%]	$a_{90/95}$ [m/s]	PFA [%]
Peak to peak amplitude	--	0.53	0.312	0.10	74.912	0.00	2618	0.82
Time delay	--	0.90	--	0.35	--	0.58	--	0.44
Frequency Amax	--	0.12	0.687	0.00	61.537	0.10	2828	0.15
Frequency Shift	--	0.25	1.685	0.08	51.386	0.27	2419	0.90
Attenuation	NA	NA	0.506	0.05	66.134	0.00	3118	0.12

The detectability of weak bonds is reported to be more challenging in comparison to debonding defects for adhesive bonds. Generally, MAPOD calculations agree with the literature and suggest that

the defect detection in debonding can be performed with a higher probability than the defect detection in weak bond cases.

The application of these results can be implemented into a quality control inspection system, where the debonding defect can be detected with peak-to-peak amplitudes and weak bonds with attenuation and frequency shift. This type of application may allow the automatic inspection for the adhesive bonding parts with high reliability, therefore expanding their usage and application areas. On the other hand, overall the most sensitive response signal feature in all cases is observed as attenuation, which depends on the ratio change from top reflection of adhesive to the bottom reflection. It is sensitive to the changes in bonding quality no matter the reason for weakening. However, it should be noted that in order to obtain such a response signal, one should differentiate from top ultrasonic reflection from the bottom reflection –which requires high frequency investigations. Although scanning acoustic microscopy offers high frequency-high resolution imaging with a quite fast inspection, the choice of high frequency transducers might limit the application to relatively thin samples, since the transducer focal length is usually small for high frequency models. The investigations are performed and modeled with high frequency (50 MHz) scanning acoustic microscopy in laboratory conditions. It must be noted that the change in frequency of the investigation and environment might affect the reliability curves significantly. High frequency selection is crucially important because when frequency is reduced thin adherend and adhesive causes interface echoes to be overlapped.

6. Conclusion

Model assisted probability detection curves for three different bonding quality cases (debonding, weak bond due to release agent, weak bond due to faulty curing) were estimated with five different signal response features (peak to peak amplitude, time delay, frequency Amax, frequency shift, attenuation). It is concluded that:

- The detection probability of debonding mostly depends on the gate selection algorithm and ultrasonic echo amplitude.

- For similar reliability, weak bond detection requires more delicate evaluation than debonding detection - frequency based calculations can improve detection reliability of the weak bond due to release agent contamination.
- Probability of the detection of weak bonds caused by faulty curing is highest using the attenuation feature.
- While the quantitative comparison is difficult due to different characteristic defect properties, MAPOD results show that the probability of detection for small sized debonding defect is higher than weak bond detection probability.
- Among all signal response features investigated, the best performed is attenuation while time delay is evaluated as the worst one.

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CRedit Author Statements

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